

Abstract

Discussion on souls, evidence of reincarnation and connection with synchronicity, with case studies.

Evidence of reincarnation and global synchronicity

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1 Intro

In my works[1], I have presented a definition of a soul, a lot of reason (logic) and evidence for its existence.

By definition, reincarnation of souls is implied to exist, as oscillation of mass due to coupling and decoupling of souls with matter.

I have defined soul as a graviton particle in my theory of Complete Relativity[2] (CR) and coupled soul to consciousness in follow-up work[3].

Depending on one's perspective, the evidence for reincarnation may be overwhelming, abundant, scarce or non-existent (confirmation bias exists in both, believers and non-believers).

In my case, I was a non-believer (in both, reincarnation and synchronicity) before my consciousness transformed. However, I cannot be satisfied with beliefs not based on a strong theoretical background. And the theory that would predict souls and reincarnation *came* to me in the form of Complete Relativity[2].

Evidence, in my case, came after the hypotheses on reincarnation[3] were developed.

The phenomena that confirm these hypotheses are also hypothesized to be increasing in frequency with accelerated evolution, so the perspectives should be shifting from scepticism to affirmation and acceptance globally too.

This is consistent with my other hypothesis - that I am one of general precursors[4].

Here, cases that certainly can be interpreted as evidence for reincarnation will be presented. As most of my work, this will be updated as new evidence becomes available to me.

UPDATE 2022.09.20: This article was originally titled "Evidence of reincarnation". However, eventually it became obvious that evidence for reincarnation is likely to be coupled (synchronized) with evidence of synchronicity occurring on global scale. Therefore, the article has been expanded and will now include the list of global synchronicity events that I encounter, even if some may not be obviously correlated with reincarnation.

2 The importance of instinct

It is commonly thought that behaviour labelled as instinct is pre-programmed or genetically inherited behaviour. But it has been shown recently that at least some of that behaviour is not inherited rather developed, sometimes even during embryonic stage[5].

However, there's still some apparently instinctive behaviour that's difficult to explain as being physically innate or developed/learned during lifetime.

The inter-species oscillation of souls, which, among other things, should contain some memory of past but also effectively future incarnations, provides another source of instinct that can explain odd or mysterious behaviour.

By my hypotheses, souls and bodies co-evolve, in such way that one is effectively driving evolution of the other - symmetrically or asymmetrically. If body genetics and equivalent soul genetics would be perfect copies of each other and in symmetric conditions, one of these (soul or body) would be obsolete. In CR, however, absolute equivalence is impossible, current effects on energy on one scale are different than current effects on energy on the other scale and exchange of information between scales will lead to relative synchronization - phase shift between evolutions on one scale and the other will oscillate and these will therefore be more or less synchronized, but difference can be absolute 0 only for absolute 0 time.

During accelerated evolution before the synchronization (and synchronicity!) maximum, it is not only the differences between soul and body that should decrease, but differences between species the soul is oscillating (reincarnating) between.

Thus, we should be seeing increasing similarity in behaviour between entangled species (species between which a particular soul oscillates), e.g., between homo.polarized[6] and domestic canine species, or between whales and homo.neutralum[6] species. This behaviour then should be attributed to *instinct* coded in the soul.

Not all individuals of particular species oscillate equally. Per my hypotheses, there are 3 major subspecies of any species[6], with possible significant differences in behaviour - which is often a precursor to physical changes. Thus, evolution of particular species should generally branch into different paths, while entangled subspecies between two different species may converge to one.

3 The importance of discontinuities

While souls and bodies may couple at conception, during growth, soul (more precisely, its constituent particles) will encounter discontinuities in time, while coupled matter encounters discontinuities in space.

Each discontinuity is associated with an energy level. Between energy levels, matter generally grows or decays continuously with exponential progression, while soul moves between them instantly relative to matter.

Thus, there will exist a phase shift between soul and matter and, in case of growth, progression of matter toward a particular state will be preceded by the *jump* of the soul to that particular state (or, more precisely, to its correlated equivalent on the scale of the soul).

In case of decay, progression (or regression) of matter may precede the soul *jump*.

In any case, changes in energy level occur when matter and soul become synchronized at the same energy level in space/time. This synchronization is also the moment when risk of death is highest, but it is also the moment one may experience a maximum of synchronicity[7] events.

Generally, one such discontinuity in time is the moment of birth, when body leaves the uterus (or egg).

Note that a uterus wall (or egg shell) is a mark of that discontinuity in space. However, not all discontinuities in space will necessarily be observable by the observer.

Limitations on growth depend on the size of environment (maximum size of population) and this will be genetically coded. Increase in this limit requires fusion of souls, halving the maximum population.

However, according to CR[2], growth in space with a change in energy level, generally slows down speed in time (which is also the limiting speed in space).

Due to limits in growth, souls will generally oscillate between birth (or conception) and death. Although oscillations between energy levels during lifetime (age reversals) are possible, these are likely to be happening during strong

changes of environment, when it is unstable.

4 The importance of birthdays

Since moment of birth is a discontinuity, it may often be associated with synchronicity.

A soul may be stable in a particular energy level, but, according to CR, its radius cannot be constant (all orbits are elliptical), it must oscillate *around* that level, even if this oscillation is generally negligible.

From time to time, however, it will be receiving and emitting pulses of stronger energy, when it will briefly *jump* (expand or collapse) to another discontinuity.

While vacuum of soul's space may be interpreted as time by one, this time is space for the soul's constituent particles (soul is a graviton), but soul can be a composite of particles at different energy levels (orbits). Such is the *carbon* soul.

Since moment of birth is a discontinuity in time, if one or more of these particles are entangled with angular momentum of the Earth's soul, these may be encountering this discontinuity in time every year.

Note how, for trees and many other organisms (likely all *carbon* souls), such encounters are also marked in space.

This explains why birth dates are common in events of synchronicity.

Note that some particles may be entangled with Earth's spin momentum - this is why one goes to sleep daily. Some are entangled with the Moon, while some with other bodies of the Solar System.

This is why not all parts of a body age the same.

From my experience, birthdays do seem to be common markers of important synchronicity events. This could be the reason why people started celebrating birthdays. I suspect fading of synchronicity events was synchronized with increase in consumerism, turning even birthdays into a celebration of consumerism. This is why one is more likely to experience synchronicity on a birthday when one is not celebrating it.

Note, however, due to the fact that number of days in a year according to our calendars is variable, events of synchronicity may not occur exactly on one's birthday, rather a day before or after.

4.1 Astronomical blunders of astrology

Obviously, entanglements between a human soul and close celestial bodies do exist, and these are mirrored in body function (although, here, some phase shifts can exist).

With discontinuities in souls and synchronicity, even birthdays become meaningful.

Once one stops celebrating birthdays and starts experiencing synchronicity, with each birthday, one will be looking forward to his next birthday, rather than remain meaninglessly counting the meaningless past ones.

Therefore, astrology may have some source in this knowledge. However, like everything else in the hands of western society, it has been corrupted to serve the needs of needy.

Western astrology, as it doesn't care for astronomy, is completely fake. However, old Vedic astrology may not be meaningless, but even if it is not, I find it likely to be misinterpreted today.

5 Evidence of reincarnation, and correlated phenomena

If an animal in the wild starts expressing behaviour that was not previously observed in the wild, but was observed in captivity, then such behaviour becomes the evidence for the existence of souls and soul oscillation (reincarnation), assuming, of course, that this animal is not the descendant of an animal that was in captivity.

A humpback whale showing such behaviour, for instance, would be a strong evidence for inter-species soul reincarnation, considering the fact that no humpback whales were ever in captivity, but other whales (and a lot of other animals) did.

I do hypothesize entanglement between life-forms and information transfer with changes in entanglement (which can be interpreted as a mechanism behind morphic fields hypothesized by R. Sheldrake), even inter-species, however, information transfer inter-species is much weaker than intra-species (unless there exists a symbiotic relationship between individuals) so it is unlikely to explain the behaviour on its own. However, this entanglement and inter-species soul oscillation are correlated, so the solution to the observed behaviour is probably best explained as a superposition of the two phenomena (soul oscillation and entanglement). Positive feedback can exist between the two, resulting in convergence of species (which I find most likely for individuals in symbiosis).

5.1 Southern right whale (2021.09.01)

Not only has the above been observed recently, the phenomena was even more interesting because it was recorded by a drone camera by *chance* and the person interacting with the whale had a birthday the same day.

To be precise, observed whales were not humpback whales, rather Southern Right whales, although these are similar, particularly in behaviour.

Now, what are the odds of a never-observed whale-human interaction happening on a birthday of interacting human, all at the same time being recorded by camera of a photographer who was there by chance?

Apparently, this was recorded on my birthday too[8] (2021.09.01), so this becomes even more remarkable.

Obviously, this is an event of synchronicity which probably has a deeper meaning. And deeper meaning I see here is the evidence of reincarnation.

Whales in the wild don't generally approach humans looking for interaction, it is the other way around.

While humpback whales are known to be gentle and compassionate giants (they are known to help individuals of other species in trouble[9]), no one was in trouble here.

Here, a southern right whale is giving a gentle nudge with its flipper to paddle boarder[10]. Where did that come from?

Traits commonly associated with humans are increasingly being observed in wild animals. Some might argue that these existed before in the wild and that we are only noticing it now, but is it so?
Weren't *our* excuses for extermination of wild animals based on differences and non-existence of such traits?
Did *we* lie ourselves or are we witnessing *lateral* transfer of traits on massive scale? Isn't this too fast and too specific to be a product of random genetic mutations and natural selection?
There is no doubt *we* lied ourselves to some degree regarding these phenomena, but obviously, something else is going on here too.

Sure, these may not be adult whales and this can be interpreted as action out of curiosity, but why this particular action and why it hasn't been observed before?

A soul that was previously in a whale that died in captivity reincarnated in

a southern right whale expressing previously common and trained behaviour compressed as an instinct and stored in soul (then reflected in epigenome), is my interpretation. The fact that this was not an adult whale, goes in favour of the hypothesis, as children are more likely to act based on instinct, and I think we can all agree - if this is instinct, it didn't emerge from inherited genetics/epigenetics of the body, because that one would be more likely to tell this animal to stay away from humans.

5.2 Bonobo pets (2022.09.01)

A remarkable synchronicity - again, on my birthday (2022.09.01) another example of *domesticated* behaviour in wild animals gets published.

Perhaps I could find more examples of this if I would be searching for them. But I never felt the need to do that and now it's clear why - I do not have to. I will simply encounter them on my birthday in the news of the day.

Bonobo apes in captivity do care for individuals other than their own species. In the wild, they do not - they mainly eat fruit and only occasionally hunt and when they catch their prey there is no genuine care, dinner might only get delayed if the ape is full.

However, now a bonobo ape has been observed cuddling a pet mongoose[11] in the wild. And the mongoose was not eaten, the ape released it afterwards.

Again, one can interpret that as coincidence, one can choose to believe that this was always present in the wild, that it simply happens rarely and it was only observed now due to increase in human population and monitoring. But I have long stopped believing in coincidence.

This is accelerated evolution - differences between wild and domestic species are annihilating. In space, it may be manifested in horizontal transfer of gene regulation patterns, in time, soul oscillation between species exchanging information. But it would be wrong to discriminate one over the other - sometimes the soul will stimulate epigenetic changes, sometimes vice versa, and both are probably required for information to get encoded anywhere.

This was not the only notable event of synchronicity of the day. An earthquake rocked Liechtenstein Parliament... during earthquake debate[12]. I have predicted before that synchronicity events will be increasing globally, I just didn't predict they will be increasing on my birthday.. but it makes sense, if one of my other hypotheses is true...
It's funny, not that I need presents, but nowadays the only present I get for my birthday is the one from god (and this year I got two). Does that

make me poor or a rich man?

Well, I may be poor in clothes and pride, but in the spirit of the mind I'm probably one of the richest men on Earth... and as things are progressing I may soon be walking naked.

With no polarized people around, that would even be cool (perhaps even literally). Who wears clothes in the garden of Eden?

No one leaves hell with their clothes on, and only some leave it with their body on.

5.3 Monkey cowboys (2023.09.01)

Nothing much interesting this birthday. However, interesting animal behaviour has been published again by BBC News[13]. Among other photos, here a monkey is riding a deer, in the wild. Evidence of inter-species soul oscillation, or independently evolved instinct (recently, considering it's a rare sight)?

If monkeys are, on average, getting more intelligent while humans, on average, are getting less intelligent, the evidence goes in favour of inter-species soul oscillation (reincarnation). It would also be an evidence that souls drive evolution of behaviour.

5.4 General evidence in peculiar behaviour

Patterns of behaviour shared across different distantly or closely related species are in some cases difficult to explain without some horizontal transfer (or sharing) of information inter-species. In some cases it is possible that behaviour has been learned through observation. This can certainly be the case with domestic animals, but animals living in the wild do not commonly learn by observing humans nor are they commonly trained by humans to perform specific tasks. Yet, there are cases of stunning display of intelligence in wild species, peculiar interaction between different species and very interesting interaction with human species.

Consider the case of a wild injured lemon shark approaching a diver and clearly asking for help[14] (it had a large fishing hook attached to its belly).

How did the shark know that a human can help her? Lemon sharks have poor eyesight and, while they can see shapes, they probably can't resolve fingers or notice a particular structure and flexibility of a human hand that can be utilized to remove a hook from its belly?

Note that sharks in general can easily mistake humans for other animals when they rely mostly on eyesight. Studies show that juvenile sharks certainly do not use eyesight to distinguish between people and prey[15].

Thus, one can probably rule out the possibility that the shark learned this by observing, using its eyesight, humans helping others. They obviously can distinguish between a human and a sea lion by other means (although sometimes a small bite or bump is needed to be sure) but can they distinguish between different types of interaction and what is the possibility that this shark has previously "observed" a human helping some other animal (and concluded that one is actually helping the other). And would she approach just any human or has she detected that this one is likely to help?

Once could argue that the shark may have been approaching different animals for help and it just got lucky by approaching this human but how plausible is that? I don't believe a part of baby shark's curriculum is "On the search for help from other species" as much as I do believe "Preying on sea lions" is. They generally don't get injured in a way other animals could help them.

There are not many species preying on sharks and those that do, don't leave hooks in their bodies. Any injury that was not caused by humans directly or indirectly will either get healed by itself or will result in death but the shark will certainly not end up on an "operating table" of a sponge called Bob.

Humans are those who can and do injure sharks in a way only humans can help them and this shark somehow knew that. Perhaps she learned it from another shark (or some other animal?) who got helped by humans (but may have not asked for help). What are the odds of that?

Was she aware that humans are the cause of her trouble and that's why she was turning to humans for help? I can see mainstream believers *texting lol's* now, but seriously, I'd like to know what's going on here - "coincidence" is not an answer, it's a convenient excuse for lack of imagination that would lead to explanation.

If the shark didn't learn this then it would have to be an instinct. Again, one that Darwinism or neo-Darwinism cannot explain - at least not without involving some kind of coincidence, which is, again, never an explanation.

This is inter-species sharing of information. Either resonance of souls in action or relatively horizontal transfer of information through inter-species soul oscillation (reincarnation) manifested here as instinct.

This is not the only case of wild animals turning to humans for help. One very interesting case is the interaction with a distressed humpback whale[16].

Another interesting case is a recently observed orangutan treating his wounds[17]. He picked a plant with medicinal properties, chewed it into a pasta, applied the

pasta to his wound, and then decided to rest for a while. Sure, this behaviour could be something we all inherited from a common ancestor, but why it hasn't been observed before? Injuries are not uncommon to these animals.

5.4.1 Human-like showering in elephants (2024.11.11)

Elephants have been observed using a water-hose to shower in a similar way humans do[18]. This was observed in a zoo, not in the wild, but it's still interesting as the animals were not trained to do that, and it is an expression of human-like behaviour that's probably correlated with inter-species information sharing. Information sharing is more pronounced in species living in close proximity, and interacting. Just like humans interacting with dogs are becoming more similar to dogs and dogs interacting with humans are becoming more similar to people. Now, we're seeing that in elephants as well. If this behaviour of elephants becomes common, their trunks may eventually start becoming more like human hands. Interesting then is the behaviour of the younger elephant in the study, who is commonly stepping on the hose while the other is showering, after being trained actually NOT to step on hoses. This can be interpreted as subconscious signalling to the other elephant that it will lose some characteristics of its trunk (or, more generally, some "elephantiness") if it continues behaving like that. This is not surprising considering that children's behaviour is more subconscious than conscious (proportionally to how young they are), and subconsciousness, and thus instinctive behaviour, is more correlated with the future and past than the present. This is why one should think twice before being angry at children behaving in a similar way (e.g., being jealous of a family dog). Short-term and long-term correlated interpretations of phenomena always exist, may commonly differ much and may simultaneously be true. In the *short-term interpretation*, the behaviour may be interpreted as bad, in the long-term good, or, *vice versa*.

It is usually good to respect the elders, for their experience of the past can be valuable. It is usually good to respect the young ones, for their inexperience of the past can show one future.

5.4.2 Other interesting animal behaviour that could be correlated with inter-species soul oscillation

Flying squirrel fakes a crime scene[19]. Dog plays a piano and sings when left alone[20]. Dolphin talks to himself[21]. Mice give first aid (CPR) to unconscious mice[22] (note that these mice have never observed the procedure so the phenomenon is attributed to instinct).

Wild chimpanzees have been observed exhibiting empathy, even tending to the wounds of other animals they weren't related to, also exhibiting human-like

hygiene habits[23] (e.g., using leaves to wipe themselves after defecating).

5.5 Other evidence

I have hypothesized previously that it is young children who should be more likely to recall information from a past incarnation (although exceptions are possible). I have also hypothesized that recalled events will generally be those leaving strong imprints in memory, e.g., violence and death (although exceptions are possible). Another hypothesis was that DNA mutations are correlated with information in soul memory (and that the soul should generally couple to DNA that is to some extent matching its own genetic code).

Well, apparently, all this has been observed even years before I developed the hypotheses. There's a fine article[24] in Scientific American from a sceptic who may be transforming into a believer (like I myself have transformed).

The article is based on works of I. Stevenson and J. B. Tucker[25] who have studied children remembering past lives. Notable are the studies of K. S. Rawat and T. Rivas as well. The case of Shanti Devi may be the most famous and is, certainly, very convincing[26].

Additional evidence for the existence of souls and reincarnation is provided in my other works, something new and very interesting has just been added to my B.Log[27].

5.5.1 Criticism

Apart from my works, it seems that most evidence of reincarnation comes from children remembering past lives.

It is possible that at least some cases are not genuine cases of remembrance of past lives, but it is also probably unlikely that none of them are.

If studies, such as those of I. Stevenson, are flawed, as some claim[28], why are there no better studies on the subject?

It seems that most criticism comes from those who, with prejudice, effectively fear reincarnation. They simply label it as superstition, with no interest to confirm or refute the results in scientific manner.

One common objection is that in most impressive cases children knew friends and relatives of the dead individual. But this is precisely what could be expected by the hypothesis of genetic matching (entanglement). In the hypothesis, probability for coupling of a soul and a body is effectively a function of spatio-temporal distance between death and conception and genetic compatibility (distance in correlation) between a dying and forming life-form. Thus, it should not be surprising that the soul would reincarnate in a close body - if conception and death are relatively synchronized.

By the hypothesis, the soul is also oscillating in mass (scale) and may couple with a body of different species before it couples again with a human body. If this species is common in the area, the soul again won't travel far before coupling (note that we do share a lot of DNA with other species and change in scale should then be correlated with changes in epigenome).

This then explains the difference in time passed between death and conception between human incarnations, if there is any. Finding a nearby [and probably domestic] animal [or, animals] with a [total] lifespan corresponding to *missing* time can then be interpreted as evidence. It would be interesting to investigate between what species particular souls are oscillating.

When uncoupled, the graviton (soul) may not be in the form of a particle, a wave (non-localized form) could be a better interpretation. As such it is travelling at, or close to, the speed of light, however, as a constituent quantum of Earth's space (gravitational well) it has a range and it is orbiting around Earth's centre. Probability for coupling is then highest at the same orbital, it's just a question how this orbital should be modelled - as a three-dimensional wave-like sphere surface or a ring (torus, or tube)?

If the soul (graviton) is polarized it should be a constituent quantum of polarized space - a magnetic field *line* (tube). In that case, location of coupling will be dependent on angular momentum of that tube. As the soul oscillates in mass, depending on frequency, it could be that it is in human compatible form roughly at the same place with each orbit (rotation). In any case, the number of possible locations for coupling is quantized.

However, Earth's magnetic field closely follows Earth's rotation (while gravitons forming the magnetic field tube travel at speed of light along the tube, the tube itself is moving slower). Therefore, coupling location may be relatively fixed to certain longitude but can be less limited in latitude (depending on frequency of mass oscillation).

Graviton mass oscillation may be interpreted as alternative explanation for coupling at the same location, however, it is probably synchronized with genetic matching.

If the soul is neutral (non-polarized) it is a constituent particle of gravitational field, not electro-magnetic, and it should have a different shape, however, it is still bound to the effective gravitational field *line* (orbital) and the sole difference may be in orbital inclination to Earth's equator. Note, however, per my hypotheses, force fields in general are compositions of electro-magnetic (polarized) and gravitational fields. Therefore, a single soul can be interpreted as relative superposition of a polarized component (soul) and a neutral component (soul). In souls considered neutral, polarized component is subdued, in other, vice versa.

In any case, dominant component is likely to be more correlated with the coupling location.

Note that polarized souls have good probability for coupling with bodies in Earth's interior, while for neutral souls, a change in [orbital] energy level is required (gravitational field *lines* are orbitals of Earth's centre or Earth's large scale graviton, they're not emerging from one Earth's pole

and entering on the other).

Obviously, if Earth's magnetic field is decreasing strength, magnetic field tubes are contracting and receding into Earth's interior - decreasing probability for surface incarnation.

This is consistent with the hypothesis of planetary neurogenesis[29] which suggests that major massive extinctions are relative extinctions - instead of going extinct, some life is transferred into mantle layers. Well, at least the souls of polarized life if not the bodies. Transfer of bodies, however, cannot be excluded. As polarized brains are shrinking, sensitivity to Earth's magnetic field may be increasing, which could be synchronized with the formation of instinct for north/south migration.

The Earth only has to ensure a tunnel for transfer. As I have hypothesized before, melting of Antarctica might just be synchronized with a manifestation of an entrance to the *promised* underworld.

Another objection is regarding poor children remembering wealthy lives or belonging to a higher caste. It is speculated that such cases may represent a scheme to obtain money from the family of the alleged former incarnation. However, in my theories, reincarnation and karma are strongly coupled. Therefore, such cases could be interpreted as karma. Reincarnation can be synchronized with karma in which case one may oscillate between *poor* and *rich* incarnations.

Then there are critics who simply mock people like I. Stevenson without providing real arguments. Some, however, admit that the phenomenon could be real, C. Sagan, in example, called for more research. But research only comes after one stops mocking what one doesn't understand. Are *we* done mocking reincarnation and karma in the West?

6 Evidence of global synchronicity, and correlated phenomena

I have previously predicted global increase in synchronicity. Here, I will publish evidence of global synchronicity as I encounter it.

I will not publish personally experienced events (there's too many of these), unless correlated with a global event.

6.1 (2022.09.01) Liechtenstein earthquake

Earthquake rocked Liechtenstein Parliament during earthquake debate[12]. This one was synchronized with reincarnation evidence (see above), and with my birthday.

UPDATE 2023.09.01

No notable earthquakes on my birthday today, but there's a 100-year anniversary[30] of the big earthquake that killed more than 100,000 people in Japan on 1923.09.01.

6.2 (2022.09.19) Mexico earthquakes

Strong earthquake (Richter magnitude >7) hit Mexico City on September 19th, 2022[31]. This is the 3rd such earthquake occurring at the same place on the same day (Sept. 19) in the last 37 years. The other two occurred in years 1985 and 2017. Statistically, probability for this is very low[32]. The meaning of this? It could be interpreted as announcement, if not confirmation, of increase in strong seismicity and/or synchronicity (note how the period between synchronized events is shrinking). I would not be surprised if there's a strong earthquake in Mexico City on 2024.09.19 but one cannot be sure of that with no detailed analysis of seismicity in Mexico and with such a limited dataset.

However, there are other signals pointing to something big on roughly the same date[33]. Thus, I wouldn't even be surprised if that earthquake is synchronized with a nuclear weapon detonating somewhere nearby. But, let's not haste with conclusions. The date (2022.09.19 \pm 1) might not be so special and might not signal anything significant, or it might have a personal meaning.

Interestingly, on the day of the earthquake I had a conversation with a friend (who I rarely encounter) whose birthday is on Sept. 20.

Also interesting is the fact that, while I was writing this, I switched to the tab with Google Maps loaded and the location of the Chicxulub crater (Mexico) was tagged (I guess it was the last location I searched for in Google Maps). Cuba is very near. Was the Cuban Nuclear Missile Crisis of 1962 simply a precursor to the crisis of 2024?

In any case, all this seems to signal some bomb will fall and the Earth will tremble, will it be an asteroid, a nuclear bomb or both in the same year? Or have I gone too far in interpretation considering the limited dataset? Time will tell.

But if the prediction proves to be correct, it will also be evident that global synchronicity events are strongly correlated with my self even if not occurring on my birthday.

Some say that people experiencing synchronicity commonly delude themselves that they are being special. But are we not relatively special? I certainly do not know many people constructing new theories in physics or even experiencing as much synchronicity as I do.

I'd say some people delude themselves into thinking that we're all equal,

failing to recognize that we're diverging into separate species, even though it's clear that, mentally, we're operating on very different levels.

Or are they really just cynical, consciously or unconsciously jealous (as polarized people commonly are) of our effective communication with higher intelligence?

Apparently, the September could be declared the month of synchronicity. Almost. But there's still 10 days left of it...

6.3 (2022.09.21) Whale stranding

Some 230 whales stranded on Tasmanian beach today[34]. Two years ago, same harbour, same month, same day (2020.09.21), same species (pilot whales) - 470 whales stranded[35].

And only 1 day ago (2022.09.20), at least 14 sperm whales got stranded some 270 km to the north[36].

I find the number of stranded whales interesting - the number of whales stranded two years ago was roughly double the number of whales stranded today.

The periodic $2^{\pm n}$ law is common in nature (e.g., doubling of cells during embryonic development). This suggests that on 2024.09.21 or 2024.09.20 (taking into account that 2024 is the leap year) there should be 110-122 pilot whales stranded here.

So this becomes another signal pointing to something extraordinary in the week 2024.09.16 - 2024.09.22.

2024.09.23

Nothing like this seems to have happened during the past week. There was a mass stranding of pilot whales (77 individuals) this year, but more than 2 months earlier, on July 11th[37], and it was not in Tasmania, rather Scotland (Orkney), where mass stranding seems to be on the increase lately, both in magnitude and number of events (this and last year were record-setting years since at least 1990[38], last year, on July 16th, 55 pilot whales have been found stranded in Scotland[39]). Orkney is on the other side of the world, nearly antipodal to Tasmania. Apparently, some mass stranding hotspots exist for

these whales (although they are not the sole species stranding at these locations[40]). It seems that, lately, if they do not strand in Tasmania, they strand in Scotland. And it seems to happen at least in the same month of the year (July in Scotland, September in Tasmania), if not at the same day. If mass stranding occurred in Scotland in this and last year, perhaps next year it will occur in Tasmania. I find these events interesting as they may be correlated with the decreasing strength of the magnetic field and movement of magnetic poles (which has accelerated lately) and anomalies in that field correlated with solar storms (the influence of which is increasing with decreasing magnetic field strength), but also with human-generated pollution (noise, chemical, ...).

6.4 (2022.10.01) Pseudo-random lottery

It's early to tell but the randomness of lotteries may be decreasing.

Two years ago, on 2020.12.01, the numbers drawn in South Africa's lottery were: 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10[41] (20 people won).

Now, on 2022.10.01, the numbers drawn in Philippines lottery were: 9, 18, 27, 36, 45, 54[42] ($n \times 9$, where n goes from 1 to 6), 433 people won (the highest number of people to have ever won the Grand Lotto's top prize, according to local sources).

Here, what's perhaps even more interesting than the combination itself is the number of people that won. Apparently, people in Philippines tend to bet regularly on sequences of numbers following some pattern.

Statistically, due to great number of lotteries around the world, unusual patterns such as these should come up from time to time, but the average interval between them should be on the order of decades, not years. If this repeats within the next 2 years then it would be reasonable to suspect that something deeper is going on here.

I have my theories, of course. What is the common denominator for Philippines and South Africa? Well, it appears to be high poverty coupled with high inequality. South Africa is one of the most unequal countries in the world, with 55.5% of population living in poverty[43] - at the national upper poverty line. In Philippines, 23.7% were below the national poverty line in year 2021[44], and the country has one of the highest rates of income inequality in the world[45].

Note that it is the indigenous population that suffers the most in countries like these.

And poor people are the ones playing lottery the most[46]. Synchronicity and spirituality are highly correlated and those who lack material possessions

generally are more spiritual (although this is not a rule).

In my example too - I have only started experiencing synchronicity after soul transformation when my material intelligence was subdued significantly while the spiritual one inflated significantly.

With poverty and inequality in the world being generally on the rise (at least in *democratic* capitalistic systems), global synchronicity should then be increasing too.

Here, probably, the high amount of spirituality is effectively deciding the outcome of lottery through subconscious mental entanglement (which is physical at some scale, according to CR).

I have predicted that during accelerated evolution the cycles of karma are compressing and the poor and rich states of individuals will be trading places more frequently - during one and the same incarnation, rather than spanned between multiple incarnations.

So this could be interpreted simply as karmic oscillation, however, as common for synchronicity, there are other interpretations and they all may be true.

In example, I don't have the money to buy a lottery ticket but my wishes are effectively becoming true. By my general precursor theory[4], this too should be increasing globally and this could be the evidence for that. The more spiritual people wish for the same thing, the probability for it becoming true is probably increasing.

This can be interpreted as local god fulfilling wishes of spiritually rich or materially poor. In yet another interpretation, this is simply a manifestation of entanglement between past and effective future - spiritually rich are simply predetermined (coded) to wish for things that are about to happen in future.

This entanglement is not a recently emerged phenomenon, it always existed, it's only now, during accelerated evolution, that it becomes noticeable - when wishes are becoming true during one and the same incarnation.

I don't play dice for money, but I believe there's a good chance that in 2024, if not sooner, the news will repeat, with at least 10 times more winners. My guess: 4, 12, 20, 28, 36, 44 (8666 winners, somewhere around Venezuela or Nicaragua).

What is also interesting here is the correlation with whale stranding. The interval between events (2 years) is the same, even the years are the same, and the numbers of stranded whales and lottery winners are following the similar *law*:

$$N(i, j) \approx N(0, 0) \times 2^i \times 10^j$$

In case of whales, however, there is no vertical component ($j=0$) of energy changes, in case of lottery, both components are present ($j=i$).

As in the case of whale stranding, this prediction is based on a very limited dataset so the confidence is low. We live in times where certain phenomena will probably become chaotic and much less predictable. Some aspects of reality, however, should become more predictable, but even if that is the case here, just like the transition to chaos is unlikely to be smooth/stable, the transition to predictability won't be either. Perturbations (e.g., reversals) are normal before the new equilibria get firmly established.

6.5 (2024.04.21) Newfoundlanders seeking new land

About 500 Newfoundlanders were inadvertently booked on the same 3000-person Caribbean cruise this month[47]. And in addition to these 500, it appears there were many people from all around the world on the ship who are also Newfoundlanders. Note that this cruise departs from Ft. Lauderdale, Florida, USA[48], nowhere near Newfoundland (Ft. Lauderdale is some 3000 km away from Newfoundland). Only about 540,000 people live in Newfoundland, so I wonder if there's a deeper meaning behind this signal.

What I find interesting about Newfoundland is its Gros Morne National Park - the only place in the world where one can stand on the MOHO (Mohorovičić discontinuity)[49]. This could signal the predicted upcoming migration of people from north to south[50] (perhaps it will start in Newfoundland? correlated with MOHO?), but that's just my interpretation. The name "Newfoundland" is interesting in this context, it literally means "new found land", it's called *Terra Nova* in Portuguese (meaning "new land"), which is the term widely used on the island. Interestingly, in the last couple of days I was occasionally thinking about the series Terra Nova[51], although the last time I watched it was about a decade ago.

6.6 (2024.07.24) Earth's immune system booting up

For the past 4 years, *Orcinus orca* whales have been attacking ships about the Iberian peninsula[52]. Of course, scientists interpret this simply as play, that somehow became popular among this species of whales. However, even if orcas themselves consider this as play, they could be influenced subconsciously to behave like that (just like people are subconsciously guided to act as cancer). Multiple interpretations are probably correct here. Most people are not participating consciously in the destruction of the planet, why expect that the reaction of beings acting on behalf of the Earth's immune system will be conscious? It probably won't. Are our immune systems fighting diseases consciously to save us? No, on average, human immune cells/proteins are not even aware their host is alive, just like humans, on average, are not aware that Earth is alive. And

today something even more interesting happened. A breaching whale (looks like a humpback) has capsized a boat, sending two people overboard[53].

Note that orcas attacking ships seem to be mostly juveniles and teenagers. The whale in this video doesn't seem to be an adult either. That can be one reason to interpret it as play, but also not. We all know that human kids are, on average, more aware of the climate and environmental crisis than their parents are, and are thus more likely to act on it. I'm pretty sure we're gonna see this kind of "play" spreading, not only among whales, but other species as well.

This looks to me very much like a precursor to something bigger, as that scene from the series *The Swarm*[54] announced, which I actually watched recently. Nice synchronicity there. The series came out less than a year ago, and at the same time we're seeing it happening in real life. I really enjoyed the series, but it seems people, on average, didn't like it as much. I understand why, they don't like the upcoming realism where their domination of the planet is challenged... I wonder what will happen 3 years from now.

6.6.1 Updates

(2024.09.21) Retaliation Commonly, a human in sight is a reason enough for a wild animal to flee a scene. An animal that's being chased and hunted by humans is unlikely to stop and retaliate, even if that animal is capable of inflicting serious damage. Recently, however, a bear did just that[55]. A nice video on dolphin attacks[56] was published today by Kristyn Plancarte (a well-known marine biologist), as there were almost 50 recorded dolphin attacks in the last 3 years in Japan[57]. With increasing human population, increasing human stupidity and increasing coverage (cameras everywhere and in everything) more of such videos probably can be expected. However, the peak of all this is probably near but the peak of retaliation is probably not.

7 Conclusion

Like everything else, evidence is a relative *beast*. Some people don't see evidence until *the god* they believe in proclaims it as such. And even then, some may choose to follow a different *god* instead, one more aligned with their beliefs.

If my theory of accelerated evolution is correct, the evidence for reincarnation (and karma) and synchronicity will be increasingly apparent.

More and more *surprises* from wild life will emerge. Some will refer to them as miracles. Some will be changing *gods* instead. And some of us won't be surprised at all. But that's expected from relative reality.

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